

Clinical Profile of Neonates with Respiratory Distress in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Central Nepal

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Abstract: Introduction: Respiratory distress is the most common symptom complex and a major reason for neonatal intensive care unit admission for newborns. Lots of effort is yet to be applied in developing countries to reduce mortality. This present study is undertaken to study the clinical profile of neonates with respiratory distress admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital in central Nepal.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital in the central region of Nepal from 1st May 2022 to 12th December 2022 after approval from the Institutional Review Committee. A convenience sampling method was used. Data were collected from the study population after obtaining informed consent and entered into a predesigned proforma. Results: Among 368 neonates admitted to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, the prevalence of respiratory distress was 151 (41.03%). Most of the neonates were male 83 (54.96%), term 97 (64.23%), of normal birth weight 88 (58.27%), and delivered via cesarean delivery 107 (70.86%). Tachypnea was the most common presentation 144 (95%) and most of the neonates received indigenous continuous positive airway pressure on treatment 108 (71.52%). Conclusion: Respiratory distress in newborns is still a significant cause of admission to the neonatal intensive care unit and a predisposing factor for neonatal mortality and morbidity. Preventative and anticipatory measures should be further explored to decrease the burden of this condition.

Keywords: neonate, respiratory distress, preterm, Nepal.

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Introduction

Respiratory distress (RD) is the leading reason for admission to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). It accounts for half of neonatal deaths manifested by various respiratory and nonrespiratory disorders.¹

Newborns with respiratory distress commonly present with tachypnea, retraction, grunting, nasal flaring, cyanosis, and hypothermia. The commonest cause of RD in term newborns is transient tachypnea of newborns and hyaline membrane

disease in preterm.² Morbidity and mortality of neonates with RD are now on a decreasing trend due to the expansion of ventilation and surfactant replacement therapy. However, the situation in a developing country is still yet to be improved.³

Early identification and management of this condition have improved outcomes. In our region, there is a paucity of evidence regarding the clinical profile of neonates with RD, so this study aims to find out the clinical profile of newborns with RD in a tertiary care center in Nepal.

Methodology of Research

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among the neonates admitted to the NICU of Chitwan Medical College and Teaching Hospital, Bharatpur, Chitwan. This study was carried out from 1st May 2022 to 12th December 2022. Ethical approval was taken from the Institutional Review Committee, before the commencement of the study. (Reference no: CMC-IRC/077/078- 073)

The inclusion criteria of the studies were term/preterm neonates with respiratory distress within 28 days of life, and singleton babies inborn in our center. Neonates having congenital anomalies like congenital heart diseases (CHD), neural tube defects (NTD), and twin deliveries were excluded from the study. A convenience sampling method was used. A minimum sample size was calculated using the formula:

$$n = Z^2 \times (p \times q) / e^2$$

$$= (1.96)^2 \times 0.30 (1-0.30) / (0.08)^2$$

$$= 126$$

Where,

n: required minimum sample size

p: prevalence of respiratory distress among NICU admitted neonates (from previous study)⁴ q:1-p

e: margin of error, 8%

z: 1.96 at 95% confidence interval

The minimum required sample size was 126. However, a total of 151 patients who met inclusion criteria were enrolled in this study. Respiratory distress was diagnosed clinically⁵ when two of the following features were present:

- A. Tachypnea (RR>60 breaths/ minutes)
- B. Nasal flaring
- C. Intercostal recession
- D. Subcostal recession
- E. Grunting
- F. Cyanosis

A detailed history and examination findings regarding gestational age at birth, gender, birth weight, risk factors for preterm deliveries, and medical problems were entered in the predesigned proforma. After admission to the NICU, babies were thoroughly examined and monitored daily till discharge from the hospital or death. They were monitored and treated as per the NICU protocols of the hospital. Finally, data were entered and analyzed using a Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSSSTM) version 21.

Results

In a total of six months duration, 368 neonates were admitted to the Neonatal Intensive care unit, and among them, the prevalence of respiratory distress was 41.03 % (151/368). Male neonates were slightly higher than females (54.96% vs 45.03%). The admitted neonates were the majority of term age (>37 weeks, 64.23%), normal birth weight (> 2500 gm, 58.27%) with an average body weight of 2466gm. 107 (70.86%) neonates were delivered via cesarean section, most done as an emergency procedure (82.24%) and the leading reason for cesarean delivery was non- reactive CTG (28.97). (Table 1) Oligohydramnios 16 (10.59%), hypertension 10 (6.62%), and hypothyroidism 9 (5.96%) were the major comorbidities present in mothers during their pregnancies. (Table 2)

Table 1. Demographic and baseline characteristics (n=151)

Parameters	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	83	54.96%
	Female	68	45.03%
Gestational age (weeks)	Extremely preterm (<27.9)	2	1.32%
	Very pre term (28-31.9)	15	9.93%
	Late pre term (32-36.9)	37	24.50%
	Term (>37)	97	64.23%
Body weight category	Extremely low birth weight	4	2.64%
	Very low birth weight	12	7.94%
	Low birth weight	47	31.12%
	Normal birth weight	88	58.27%
Mean body weight of newborn (gm)		2466.22	
Mode of delivery:	Vaginal	44	29.10%

Types of Cesarean Delivery(N=107)	Cesarean	107	70.86%
	Elective	19	17.75%
	Emergency	88	82.24%

Table 2. Maternal risk factors of pregnant mothers with neonates at NICU

Risk factors	Frequency (n=151)	Percentage
Oligohydramnios	16	10.59%
HTN	10	6.62%
Hypothyroidism	9	5.96%
Obstetric cholestasis	6	3.97%
Gestational Diabetes	5	3.31%
DM	5	3.31%
Hypertensive disorder pregnancy	3	1.98%
Rh-negative pregnancy	2	1.32%
Rheumatic heart disease	1	0.66%
Hyperthyroidism	1	0.66%
Polyhydramnios	1	0.66%
UTI	1	0.66%

Tachypnea 144 (95.36%), grunting 90 (59.60%), and chest indrawing 43 (28.40%) were the most common presentation. Most of the neonates were having multiple presentations at once. (Table 3)

Table 3. Clinical presentation of the newborns in respiratory distress on admission at NICU

Clinical Presentation on Admission	Frequency (n=151)	Percentage
Tachypnea	144	95.36%
Grunting	90	59.60%
Chest Indrawing	43	28.40%
Cyanosis	11	7.28%
Nasal flaring	7	4.63%
Poor capillary perfusion	4	2.64%
Hypothermia	3	1.98%
seizure	1	0.66%
Tracheal tug	1	0.66%

Out of 151 neonates admitted for respiratory distress, 108 (71.52%) were managed with indigenous continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) followed by Bubble CPAP on 18 (11.92%). The average CPAP utilized was 29 hours per neonate. Ventilator support was needed for 17 neonates (11.25%) with an average duration of 3 days. Phototherapy and double volume exchange transfusion have been received by 40 (26.49%) and 3 (1.98%) of the neonates who had neonatal jaundice along with respiratory distress respectively. 15 neonates (9.93%) who had a severe form of HMD received surfactant therapy (INSURE technique). There were 19 neonates (12.58%) required incubator support. Central vein catheterization was required for 15 neonates (9.93%). (Table 4)

Table 4. Status of treatment received by neonates at NICU

		Frequency (n=151)	Percentage
Oxygen Support	Nasal prongs/face-mask	3	1.98%
	Indigenous CPAP	108	71.52%
	Bubble CPAP	18	11.92%
	Ventilator	17	11.25%
Phototherapy Received	Yes	40	26.49%
Surfactant Received	Yes	15	9.93 %
Incubator Support	Yes	19	12.58%
Antibiotics support	Yes	48	31.17%
DVET	Yes	3	1.98%
Central Venous catheterization	Yes	15	9.93 %

Discussion

Among 368 neonates admitted to the NICU, the prevalence of respiratory distress was 151 (41.03%), comparable to the study conducted by Abdel Baseer KA, et al.⁶ (46.50 %) whereas the study done by Ahmed, et al.⁷ showed a slightly higher rate (58.16 %) and comparably lower in the study done by Lamichhane et al. (30.83 %).⁴

Respiratory distress in neonates is recognized as one or more signs of increased work of breathing, such as tachypnea, nasal flaring, grunting, or chest retraction. Normally, the respiratory rate in neonates ranges from 30 to 60 breaths per minute and a respiratory rate greater than 60 breaths per minute is tachypnea. Tachypnea is a common but nonspecific finding in various respiratory, cardiovascular, and metabolic disorders.⁸ Pulmonary causes of respiratory distress may be related to alterations during normal lung development or transition to extrauterine life. Common causes of respiratory distress include TTN, HMD, meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), pneumonia, and other miscellaneous causes.⁹

In our study, 107 (70.90%) neonates were delivered via cesarean section which is in line (76.55%) with a study done by Abdel Baseer KA, et al.⁶ Cesarean section without labor was significantly associated with respiratory distress in term and late preterm infants in a study by Sun H. et al.¹⁰ The reason for this association is found to be surfactant deficiency and many interventions have been introduced to lower this risk. Maternal corticosteroid administration before elective cesarean delivery is one of those interventions that has shown promising benefits in lowering respiratory distress in newborns as it enhances surfactant production and helps for better lung air exchange.¹¹

TTN is a frequent cause of neonatal respiratory distress and is due to impaired clearance of fetal lung fluid. TTN is frequently seen in babies born via elective cesarean section and usually presents with grunting and mild signs of respiratory distress. These signs usually persist for up to 48 hours and are generally self-limiting but some neonates need oxygen supplementation being admitted in the neonatal unit, accounting for approximately 10% of all term newborn admissions.¹² In our study, the major cause of neonatal distress was TTN, 80 (52.98%) followed by EONNS and HMD. This finding is comparable to a study conducted by Alok Kumar and B. Vishnu Bhat.¹³ But in contrast to our study, a study conducted by Abdel Baseer KA, et al.⁶ has reported respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) as a leading cause (49.6%) of neonatal respiratory distress, followed by TTN (22.1%).

Regarding maternal risk factors, oligohydramnios was found to be the leading factor associated with neonatal respiratory distress in our study, followed by hypertension and hypothyroidism. Oligohydramnios can result in

pulmonary hypoplasia in fetuses leading to reduced lung function and prone to respiratory problems. Contrary to our findings, studies^{6,14} have shown PROM or prematurity as a leading risk factor for the development of respiratory distress. Premature infants are more likely to develop respiratory distress syndrome (also known as hyaline membrane disease) than mature or term ones due to structural and functional immaturity of the lung (surfactant deficiency). Respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) is most evident in newborns born before 28 weeks of gestation compared to 28 to 34 weeks of gestation where RDS is prevalent in one-third of cases. In newborns completing 34 weeks of gestation, the prevalence of RDS is less than 5%.¹⁵

Management of neonatal respiratory distress can be both symptomatic and disease-specific. Detail history (antepartum and intrapartum) and examination are crucial for anticipating or diagnosing causes of distress. TTN begins early and the treatment is generally supportive as it is usually self-limiting. Neonates with RDS usually have cyanosis and require supplemental oxygen. Mild cases may respond to the CPAP, but more severe cases usually require mechanical ventilation or administration of exogenous surfactant into the lungs.¹⁶ Prenatal administration of corticosteroids between 24 and 34 weeks of gestation has been shown to lower the risk of respiratory distress syndrome when the risk of preterm delivery is high. Postnatal corticosteroid administration for RDS may decrease mortality risk, but there is an increased risk of cerebral palsy.¹⁷

Oxygen supplementation is often required in neonates admitted for respiratory distress which can be given through nasal cannula, CPAP, or mechanical ventilation in severe cases. Our study shows that the majority of neonates required oxygen support via indigenous CPAP followed by Bubble CPAP. In 17 (11.25%) neonates with severe respiratory distress, ventilator support was needed with an average of 3 days duration. Meticulous and timely use of CPAP helps to avoid pulmonary damage associated with invasive mechanical ventilation as well as ventilator-associated pneumonia. In a study by Ahmed et al.⁷, most of the infants requiring invasive ventilator support were infants with congenital pneumonia and severe sepsis. Bacterial sepsis is a common finding among neonates with respiratory distress so it is better to give antibiotics to neonates with high oxygen requirements before the blood culture report. A total of 48 (31.17%) neonates in our study received antibiotics. Thermoregulation is another important thing to consider as hypo or hyperthermia increases the metabolic demand thereby increasing the oxygen demand or quickly depleting neonates' oxygen reserve. In our study, 19 (12.58%) neonates needed incubator support for thermoregulation.

Limitations:

- Single-center study (might not accurately reflect the scenario of large geographical regions)
- Study population of only a 6-month duration has been included.

Conclusion

The prevalence of respiratory distress among the newborns admitted to the NICU was higher compared to studies done in similar settings. The majority of neonates had transient tachypnea of newborns followed by early-onset neonatal sepsis. Most of the neonates in our study responded well to treatment with very low in-hospital mortality. Premature newborns with low birth weight are more prone to develop severe respiratory distress which highlights the need for better obstetric care and proper access to advanced child healthcare services.

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